

Ashtamangal Ghrita Medicine for Intelligence: A Drug Review

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Abstract—Ashtamangal Ghrita is one formulation Mentioned in Rakshoghna (protection from the infection), enhance Medha (intellect) and Smriti. It was explained in Vagabhatta¹, Yogratnakar² and Kashyap Samhita³. It contains *Acorus calamus* Linn. (Fam. Araceae), *Saussurea lappa* C.B. Clarke (Fam. Compositae), *Bacopa monnieri* (Linn.) Wettst., Syn. *Herpestis monnieri* (Linn.) H.B. & K. (Fam. Scrophulariaceae), *Hemidesmus indicus* (Linn.) R. Br. (Fam. Asclepiadaceae), *Piper longum* Linn. (Fam. Piperaceae), *Brassica campestris* Linn. (Fam. Brassicaceae), Ghee and Saindhav.

Keywords— Vacha, Kushtha, Bramhi, Pippali, Sarshap, Ghee, Saindhav.

I. INTRODUCTION

In classical Ayurvedic texts *Lehana Karma* is done for inadequate growth and development without having any disease. Health of the child depends on *Lehana*. For *Lehana Karma*, many compounds have been prescribed in that *Ashtamangal Ghrita* is one of them, which is a polyherbal formulation as it content eight drugs –*Bramhi*, *Vacha*, *Pippali*, *Sariva*, *Kushtha*, *Siddarthaka* (*Brassica campestris*), *Saindhava* and *Ghrita*. This formulation is used as *Rakshoghna* (protection from the infection), enhance *Medha*(intellect) and *Smriti*. In Ayurveda, there are ample evidence of many nootropic drugs uses for improvement and enhancement of mental sub-capability.

Classically, it is explained in the *samhita* like *Vagabhatta*¹, *Yogratnakar*² and *Kashyap Samhita*³ and *Yogaratnakar* as:

“वचाकुष्ठं ब्राम्हीसिद्धार्थकमापि वा।
सारिवासैधवन्चैव पिप्पलीघ्नितमष्टमम्॥
मेध्यंघ्नितमिदं सिद्धं पातव्यन्च दिनैः दिनैः।
दृढस्मितिः क्षिप्रमेधाः कुमारो बुद्धिमानभवेत्।
न च पिशाचानरक्षांसि न भुतानचमातरः॥
प्रभवन्ति कुमारानां पिबताष्टमइलम्॥”¹

Aim: *Ashtamangal Ghrita* is beneficial for Intelligence

TABLE 1. Composition of *Ashtamangal Ghrita*¹:

Sr.no	Name of Drug	Latin Name	Part used	Qty
1	<i>Vacha</i> ⁴	<i>Acorus calamus</i>	Rhizomes	36 gm
2	<i>Kushtha</i> ⁵	<i>Saussurea lappa</i>	Root	36 gm
3	<i>Bramhi</i> ⁶	<i>Bacopa monnieri</i>	WholePlant	36 gm
4	<i>Sariva</i> ⁷	<i>Hemidesmus indicus</i>	Root	36 gm
5	<i>Pippali</i> ⁸	<i>Piper longum</i>	Root	36 gm
6	<i>Sarshap</i> ⁹	<i>Brassica campestris</i>	Seed	36gm
7	<i>Ghee</i> ¹⁰	-	-	1 kg
8	<i>Saindhav</i> ¹¹	-	-	36 gm
9	<i>Water</i> ¹²	-	-	4 litre

Method Preparation²

- 1) Take all the ingredients in *Kalka* form.
- 2) Mix them homogeneously in *Kalka* form
- 3) Then add 1 Kg of *Ghrita* and 4 Litres of water in it.
- 4) Keep this mixture on *Mandagni* and wait for *Ghrita sidha Lakshanas*.
- 5) Then it is stored in tight container.

Anupana: *Ko-ushna Jala*

Standard Dosage³:

- Babies - Infants: 6 months to 4 yrs: 3 ml x 2 times a day.
- Children 4yrs - 12 yrs: 5 ml x 2 times a day.

Routes of Administrations:

- Orally^{1,2,3}
- As nasya¹³

Duration:

- Can be taken as a regular dietary supplement.
- Recommended minimum usage - 12 months.

Duration

- 30 - 60 minutes before food
- With warm milk or water

Storage:

- Store in a cool dry place in tight container.
- May become solid at room temperature on cool weather
- Can be stored in refrigerator
- Use a clean dry spoon

Shelf Life: 36 months

Pharmacodynamics of Drugs

1) *Vacha*⁴:

- Latin name: *Acorus calamus*
- Family: *Araceae*
- Synonyms: *Aruna, Uragandhi, Lomasi, Bhutmashini, Mangalya*
- Rasa: *Katu, Tikta*
- Veerya: *Ushna*
- Vipak: *Katu*
- Guna: *Laghu, Tikshna*
- Part used: Rhizomes

2) *Kushta*⁵:

- Latin name: *Saussurea lappa*
- Family: *Asteraceae*
- Sanskrit Names: *kashmirij, utpal, pakal,*
- Rasa: *Tikta, Katu, Madhur*
- Veerya: *Ushna*
- Vipak: *Katu*
- Guna: *Laghu, Rukshya, Tikshna*
- Part used: Root

3) *Bramhi*⁶:

- Latin name: *Baccopa Monnerie*
- Family: *Scrophularaceae*
- Synonyms: *Smritiprada, Tikta, Medhya*
- Rasa: *Tikta, Kashay*
- Veerya: *Shita*
- Vipak: *Madhur*
- Guna: *Laghu*
- Part used: Whole plant

4) *Sariva*⁷:

- Latin name: *Hemidesmus indicus*
- Family: *Asclepidaceae*
- Synonyms: *Madhura, Vrishyaa*
- Rasa: *Madhur, Tikta*
- Veerya: *Sheet*
- Vipak: *Madhur*
- Guna: *Guru, Snigdha*
- Part Used: Root

5) *Pippali*⁸:

- Latin name: *Piper longum*
- Family: *Piperaceae*
- Synonyms: *Magadhi, vaidehi, Chapala.*
- Rasa: *Katu*
- Veerya: *ushna*
- Vipak: *Madhur*
- Part used: Fruit, Root

6) *Sarshap*⁹:

- Latin name: *Brassica campestris*
- Family: *Cruciferae*
- Synonyms: *Kalamohare, sasive, sarish*
- Rasa: *Katu, Tikta*
- Veerya: *Ushna*
- Vipak: *Katu*
- Part used: Seed

7) *Ghrita*¹⁰:

शस्तंधीस्मृतिमेधाग्निबलायुःशुक्रश्चक्षुषाम
बालवृद्धप्रजाकान्तिसौकुमार्यस्वराधिनाम॥

Ghee is apart for those who wish to enhance dhi (intellect), smriti(memory), Medha (discriminative ability), agni (Digestion/metabolism), Bala (strength), Ayu(Longevity), sukla(virility), caksus(vision). It is desirable for those who wish to have progeny, to enhance complexion, beauty and sweetness of voice.

8) *Saindhava*¹¹:

सैधवं तत्र सस्वादुवृष्यंहृद्य त्रिदोषानुत।

लघुअनुष्णदशःपथ्यमाविदाहिअग्निदीपन॥

Saindhav has slight madhurs rasa (Sweet taste) is vrsya (aphrodisiac), Hridya and pacifies tridoshas. It is Laghu, not much ushna desirable for the eyes and does not produces burning sensation during digestion but also carminative.

II. PROBABLE MECHANISM OF ACTION

- *Vacha* reduces bodily *kapha* and mental *doshas* & restores Consciousness. It is the best medicine for children to having lowered the IQ power. So, it is called as Medicine of Brain since ages⁴.
- *Kushta* used in *Vata* disease, especially, in Epilepsy since it is *Vaatahara* and Anti-Epileptic. It is also used as Appetizer and Digestive⁵.
- *Bramhi* is used in Nervous System disorders and Epilepsy is two conditions which require *Bramhi*⁶.
- *Sariva* also helps in Appetizer, Digestive and Laxatives blood purifier and Anti Inflammatory⁷.
- *Pippali* is a Brain Tonic and alleviates *Vata*. It is useful in weakness of the brain and *Vata* disorders and *Sarshap Agnivardhan. Varnykar*⁸.
- Both the Ghrita and Saindhav are also having properties which enhances the intellect and memory and discriminative ability.
- In previous study was a preliminary study experiments suggest that *Ashtamangal Ghrita* increases the brain AChE activity in developing brain. This effect was more pronounced in undernourished animals.
- Orally administered *Ashtamangal Ghrit* showed a significant increase of test parameters viz. neutrophil adhesion, haemagglutinating antibody titre (HAT) and delayed type hypersensitivity (DTH) response. In rats immunized with sheep RBC, AG enhanced the humoral antibody response to the antigen and significantly potentiated the cellular immunity by facilitating the footpad thickness response to sheep RBC in sensitized rats. With a dose of 300 mg/kg/day the values of HAT and DTH responses were 455.08 ± 0.75 and 31.0 ± 10.72 respectively, in comparison to the control group. These differences were statistically significant.
- Potency of improving intellect, improves memory recall power and retention span thereby memory enhancer action, induces alertness, improves concentration, reduces rate of cell death of neurons, improves ability of thinking and reasoning and improves concentration, alertness, and other cognitive functions.
- Nootropic effect of *Ashtamangal Ghrita* and *Jyotismati Taila* is well established in Ayurveda. *Ashtamangal Ghrita* as *Nasya* having

It also helps in Depressions and mental Retardation by enhancing Intellegency^{4,5}.

- It is easy to prepare & dispense due its availability in *Leha* form.

III. CONCLUSION

Ashtamangal Ghrita contains eight drugs mentioned in *Vagbhata*¹, *Yogratnakar*² and *Kashyap Samhita*³ in *Leha* form, which is one of formulation indicated in Nervous System diseases. It can be used in day to day practice as all the drugs are readily available and palatability is good in children.

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